

Automated Recognition of Power Quality Disturbances using Internet of Power Quality Things

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ABSTRACT

Real-time power quality (PQ) monitoring has become most essential to evaluate the severity of voltage variations for timely protecting distributed energy systems, appliances and equipment connected with internet of things (IoT) networks. In this paper, we attempt to present a low-complexity PQ disturbance (PQD) recognition method for automatically detecting variation events, such as sags, swells, interruptions and transients according to the IEEE Std.1159. The proposed PQD event recognition method consists of digital filtering, Hilbert transform (HT) and decision tree. The proposed PQD recognition method is evaluated using the simulated PQ signals according to the IEEE Std.1159 and the real-time PQ signals. The proposed method had a recognition accuracy of 96-100% for detecting the voltage sag, swell, momentary interruption, transient and combined disturbances.

Keywords: PQ – Power Quality, PQD– Power Quality Disturbance, HT-Hilbert Transform, IoPQT-Internet of Power Quality Things

1. Introduction

With the incorporating renewable energy sources, proliferation of nonlinear loads, power electronic components, the equipment utilized in power systems has become increasingly sensitive to variations in power quality (PQ), because the equipment contain power electronic components which are very sensitive to the power disturbances (M.V. Rodriguez et al. 2016). The PQ disturbance (PQD) typically manifest as variations in frequency, current, or voltage of the power signal, which could affect both electrical utilities and customers. Voltage sag, voltage swell, notch, transients, and harmonic distortions are the main reason behind the degradation in quality of power (S D. G-Lieberman et al. 2012). Identification of such disturbances will help us to improve power quality by initiating appropriate mitigation techniques. Therefore, automated PQD recognition is highly desirable for protection of power distributed network. For power quality analysis and classification of disturbances various techniques and methodologies have been studied based on the, short time Fourier transform, S- Transform, Fourier transform, wavelet transform, Kalman filter, root mean square (RMS), and empirical mode decomposition (C.I Chen et al. 2015). In this study, we aim to investigate an efficient PQD recognition approach tailored for IoT-enabled PQ monitoring systems. Our proposed method is designed to accurately detect and classify PQ disturbances while addressing resource constraints and ensuring low latency.

1.1. Related Works

In the past studies, various PQ disturbance recognition methods by using the features obtained from the time-domain, frequency-domain, and time-frequency domain and the classifiers (P. Kathirvel et al. 2011). Some of the methods utilize digital filters, discrete wavelet transform (DWT), Gabor-Wigner transform (GWT), morphology operators, chirp Z-transform (CZT), wavelet packet transform (WPT), Wigner distribution function (WDF), continuous wavelet transform (CWT), S-transform (ST), short-time Fourier transform (STFT), hyperbolic S-transform (HST), Gabor transform (GT), time-time transform (TTT), mathematical morphology (MM), empirical mode decomposition (EMD) and Hilbert-Haung

transform (HHT), sparse representation, and hybrid transforms. The general block diagram of PQD event classification is depicted in Fig. 1. In this section, we summarize the signal processing techniques and classifiers used for identifying fluctuations in power quality.

Fig. 1. Power Quality Disturbance (PQD) Classification.

In (Y. Xu et al. 2020) introduced a novel algorithm for the identifying and categorizing of PQD in the distribution networks. Nine types of power quality disturbances were analyzed. The initiation time, termination time, frequency and amplitude of disturbances are derived using Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD) and disturbances are classified by detrended fluctuation analysis (DFA). The proposed method achieves a classification accuracy of 99.4% at 30 dB. In (R. Gong et al. 2020) proposed a PQ disturbance detection and method to classify micro grids leveraging deep convolution network framework. The disturbances were identified and classified based on the trained and optimized network using gradient descent method and adaptive moment estimation technique (Adam). The precision of classification of the network is 99.1%, and the time taken for training the network is only approximately 6 minutes.

In (L. A. R. Ramirez et al. 2020) proposed a methodology for evaluating transient PQ disturbances. Genetic algorithm was used to detect the frequency, phase, and amplitude of the fundamental component from an electric signal. A fuzzy-based classifier was used with inputs derived from three advanced statistical measures (variance, sixth-order cumulant, and kurtosis) after signal suppression. Validation results using synthetic and the real signals showed that it had up to 30% more results than conventional methodologies. In (N. Kishor et al. 2020) explored the energy-efficient ensemble empirical mode decomposition (EPEEMD) method for the detection and classifying PQ disturbances using a least-square support vector machine (LSSVM). This methodology was validated for offline data using PSCAD/EMTDC and its analysis in MATLAB. Field programmable gate array (FPGA) components were employed for the real-time implementation. In (Q. Tang et al. 2020) introduced optimized S-transform (OST) to improve time-frequency resolution of window parameters using maximum energy concentration. The classification framework was proposed with integrating OST and KSVM. The performance of the methodology was analyzed on experiments on computer simulations and experimental signals demonstration with an accuracy of 97.08%.

In (Y. Xu et al. 2020) introduced a method for real-time feature extraction utilizing multi-scale fluctuation-based dispersion entropy (MFDE) and empirical wavelet decomposition. The method was simulated and verified using IEEE13 node test feeder and used SVM as the classifier. The method had achieved an accuracy of 99.73% under noiseless conditions and 99.36% at an SNR of 20 dB. In (T. Zhong et al. 2019) introduced a multiresolution S-transform (MST) technique for identifying and categorizing PQ disturbances. The dataset includes disturbance signals with noise levels ranging between 30 dB and 50 dB, facilitating the analysis of noise impact. This approach achieves a detection accuracy of 99.08% under a 30 dB noise scenario.

In (Y. Wang et al. 2019) presented the single and multiple disturbances detection in an islanded micro-grid based on DWT and normalized Renyi entropy. The SVM and KNN was used for classification. It was observed that the SVM provides better results. The detection accuracy is higher than 95%. Automatic PQ monitoring of noisy environment using Y. Wang et al. (2019) proposed a noise-suppression algorithm utilizing slip-singular value decomposition (SVD) and Hilbert transform (HT) for monitoring noisy environments. In (M. Sahani et al. 2019) introduced the reduced sample empirical mode decomposition (RSEMD) enhancing the segmentation of the power quality disturbances (PQD). The use of HT is for the PQD detection. A class specific weighted random vector functional link network (CSWRVFLN) classifier was employed for recognizing intricate PQDs. The method was evaluated, and confirmed for real-time monitoring using an FPGA-embedded processor. The method had an accuracy of 99.29% and 99.81% for real type and synthetic type of PQD events respectively.

The cross-correlation-based approach along with fuzzy logic is proposed by (S. De et al. 2018) is used for the automated PQD detection and classification in power distribution system. Eight basic and nine combinations PQD were considered for the classification. The method was validated by real operating conditions in the laboratory using data acquisition system and the developed a classifier with 100% accuracy. A tunable-Q wavelet transforms (TQWT) combined with a dual multi-class support vector

machine (MSVM) is employed as an automated recognition method for identifying power quality disturbances (K. Tirumala et al. 2018). Feedforward neural-network and decision tree-based classifiers were used for classification of PQD events. Results validated using PSCAD showed that average accuracy for noiseless and noisy conditions are 98.78% and 96.42% respectively.

1.2. Aim and Major Contributions

Although many PQD event detection and classification methods were presented using advanced signal decomposition techniques and deep learning networks and also focused on the robust detection and classification of PQD events in noise-free and noisy environments, exploring lightweight PQD event classification is most important in order to reduce latency or processing so that the timely preventive action or control signal can be generated to protect the equipment damages and also to recognize the mixture of PQD events which includes two or more PQ disturbances. Key contributions are summarized below

- By considering the resource constrained aspects and latency, this paper attempt to present an automated PQD event recognition method based on the digital filtering, Hilbert transform (HT) along with a decision tree.
- The method is presented to detect both single and combined PQD events by using simple filtering techniques.
- The PQD recognition method is evaluated using the simulated PQ signals according to the IEEE Std.1159 and the real-time PQ signals.
- The proposed method had a recognition accuracy of 96-100% for detecting the voltage sag, swell, momentary interruption, transient and combined disturbances

In this paper, section 2 presents an automated power quality disturbance (PQD) event recognition method. Section 3 presents evaluation results of the PQD event detection method using the simulated and real-time PQ signals. Finally, section 4 contains conclusion.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This paper introduces an automated method for PQD identification method for detecting voltage variations according to IEEE Std.1159-2009. Hilbert transform (HT) is used for detecting voltage magnitude. The proposed method does not require neither a specific model nor an algorithm to update its parameters. Hence the computational urden, complexity and convergence time could be reduced. Fig.1 shows the proposed PQD method, which consists of digital filtering, Hilbert transform (HT) and decision rules. In the proposed method, low-pass (LP) filters and high-pass (HP) filters are implemented to obtain the voltage variation PQ components and the transient components, respectively. The processed signal is derived from applying Hilbert transform to LP-filtered signal for extracting instantaneous amplitude (IA) envelope to detect the voltage variations. The maximum amplitude of the HP filtered signal is used for detecting PQ transients. Based on the duration of the IA envelope of the extracted transient signal, the notch, transients and noises are detected in this study. The decision rules with threshold ranges are shown in Fig.2. The detection thresholds are fixed according to IEEE Std. 1159-2009. In compared to the RMS and DFT based envelope extraction approaches for voltage variations, the HT-based instantaneous envelope extraction can provide accurate determination of the end-points of both voltage variations and transient portions in the PQ signal.

2.1. Digital Filtering for Transient Events and Waveform Variation Events Discrimination

In this study, we are using the low-pass filter (LPF) and high-pass filter (HPF) to discriminate waveform variation events from transient events. The LPF and HPF are designed with a cross-over frequency (cut-off frequency) of 1500 Hz. The 4th order Butterworth filter was designed to implement LP and HP filtering. The output of the digital filter is shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 2. Proposed PQD recognition method.

Fig. 3. Output of the digital filtering stage: (a) PQ signal with waveform variation, (b) normal PQ signal and (c) PQ signal with harmonics.

2.2. Instantaneous Amplitude Extraction from the Analytical Waveform

In this study, the instantaneous amplitude (IA) waveform is extracted from the analytical representation of the filtered signals. The proposed IA waveform can provide better determination of end points of both short duration waveform variations and long-duration waveform variations (sag, swell, and interruption) as compared to the root-mean-square (RMS) based IA waveform. Therefore, we describe the construction of the analytical waveform by using the Hilbert transform in this section. Although many techniques can be used to design Hilbert transformer, this study use the DFT for constructing the HT.

The analytical signal representation of a real-valued PQ signal $x[n]$ is determined as

$$z[n] = x[n] + j \hat{x}[n] \tag{1}$$

$$\hat{x}(t) = H[x(t)] = \frac{1}{\pi t} * x(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x(\tau)}{t - \tau} d\tau \tag{2}$$

$$\hat{X}(f) = F\left[\hat{x}(t)\right] = F\left[\frac{1}{\pi t}\right] F[x(t)] = -j \operatorname{sgn}(f) X(f) \tag{3}$$

The signum function is defined as,

$$\operatorname{sgn}(f) = \begin{cases} 1 & f > 0 \\ 0 & f = 0 \\ -1 & f < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\hat{X}(f) = IFT\left[X(\hat{f})\right] \text{ where } \hat{X}(f) = -j \operatorname{sgn}(f) X(f) = \begin{cases} -jX(f) & f > 0 \\ jX(f) & f < 0 \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

The Hilbert transform applied to a discrete-time signal is computed as

$$\hat{x}[n] = IDFT(X1[k]) \tag{5}$$

$$X1[k] = \begin{cases} -jX[k] & k = 0, 1, \dots, \frac{N}{2} - 1 \\ jX[k] & k = \frac{N}{2}, \frac{N}{2} + 1, \dots, N - 1 \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

The instantaneous amplitude (IA) is calculated as

$$IA[n] = \sqrt{x^2[n] + \hat{x}^2[n]} \tag{7}$$

2.3. Decision rules

Based on the typical duration and voltage magnitude as reported in the IEEE Recommended Practice for Monitoring Electric Power Quality, IEEE Standard 1159-2009, as in Table 1, the decision rules are constructed to detect the PQD events of sag, swell, momentary interruption (MI), transient (T), normal plus transients, sag plus transients and swell plus transients based IA waveform as constructed using the flow diagram of Fig. 4.

The decision tree with suitable thresholds for amplitude and duration are illustrated in Fig. 5.

In this study, we combine to estimate the amplitude level and duration from the IA waveforms extracted from the LP and HP filtered signals. As per the proposed method illustrated in Fig.2, the maximum amplitude of the IA waveform of the HP filtered signal is employed to identify the existence of the transients, wherein the amplitude threshold is fixed as 0.01 which was widely used in the past studies. By combining the results of each of the decision trees, the combined PQ disturbances are detected in this study.

Fig. 4. A simplified diagram of instantaneous amplitude extraction which will be used for detecting sag, swell and momentary interruption events.

Table 1. IEEE Recommended Practice for Monitoring Electric Power Quality, IEEE Standard 1159-2009.

Category	Typical Duration	Typical Voltage Magnitude
1. Transients 1.1 Impulsive 1.2 Oscillatory	< 50 ns 0.3 to 50 ms	0 to 4pu
2. Short-Duration Variation 2.1 Instantaneous 2.1.1 sag 2.1.2 swell 2.2 Momentary 2.2.1 sag 2.2.2 swell 2.2.3 Interruption 2.3 Temporary 2.3.1 sag 2.3.2 swell	0.5 to 30cycles 0.5 to 30cycles 30cycles to 3s 30cycles to 3s 0.5cycles to 3s 3s to 1minute 1s to 1minute	0.1 to 0.9pu 1.1 to 1.8pu 0.1 to 0.9pu 1 to 1.4pu < 0.1pu 0.1 to 0.9pu 1.1 to 1.2pu
3. Long-Duration Variations 3.1 Sustained interruption 3.2 Under-voltages 3.3 Over-voltages	>1minute > 1minute > 1minute	0.0pu 0.8 to 0.9pu 1.1 to 1.2pu

Fig. 5. Decision Tree for the classification of PQD events.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effectiveness of the proposed PQD event recognition approach is evaluated using simulated PQ signals and real-time PQ signals in this section. The simulated system consists of power transmission lines, with a length of 100km (line1) and 100km (line2). Lines feed an RL load. A sustained three-phase fault to ground occurring at the midpoint of line 1 is presented in this simulation. This results in an interruption on load, which causes sag wave generation. A system is developed with a three-phase supply of 25 KV 100 MVA 50 Hz. A transient model is simulated in Matlab Simulink with RL and capacitive loads supplied through a pi connected network to a three-phase supply of 25 KVA 100MVA 50HZ system.

We evaluated the effectiveness of the proposed PQ disturbance recognition approach through the use of 50 simulated PQ signals for each category of different kinds of voltage variations and transients and normal PQ signals. The findings of this study are presented in Fig.7.

Fig. 6. Decision Tree for the classification of PQD events

Fig.7. Results of the proposed method for voltage swell and transient disturbances

Table 2. Performance of the proposed method.

Signal	Normal(N)	Sag	Swell	MI	Transient(T)	N+T	Sag+T	Swell+T
Normal(N)	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sag	0	49	0	0	0	0	0	0
Swell	0	0	50	0	0	0	0	0
MI	0	0	0	49	0	0	0	0
Transient(T)	0	0	0	0	50	0	0	0
N+T	0	0	0	0	0	48	0	0
Sag+T	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	0
Swell+T	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	50

MI-Momentary Interruption

From the results as illustrated in Table 2, it is noted that the proposed PQD recognition method achieves recognition accuracy of 96-100% for detecting the voltage variations and transients. The proposed PQD method is further evaluated by using the combined PQ disturbances including the sag and transients.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an automated Power quality disturbance method is introduced based on the digital filters, instantaneous amplitude and decision rules for detecting single and combined PQDs. The proposed approach evaluated utilizing 50 PQ signals for each of the PQD categories of normal, sag, swell, momentary interruption, transient, notch plus transient, sag plus transient, and swell plus transient. The proposed HT-based instantaneous amplitude method had recognition accuracy of 96-100% in detecting single and combined power quality disturbances. For future research, the real-time implementation of the PQD recognition method will be studied using the embedded processors.

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